

Proposed Marketing Strategies for CV. Ganesha Sora to Increase Brand Awareness and Sales

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ABSTRACT: MSMEs are the most important pillars of the Indonesian economy, contributing for 61.07% of GDP or \$8,573.89 trillion rupiah. The MSME in the food processing industry is one of the most developed MSMEs. The presence of dairy products produced by these MSMEs benefits the food processing industry. The demand for dairy products in Indonesia has surged by more than 10% each year over the last ten years. Ganesha Sora is one of the MSMEs engaged in the production of dairy products that according to the company's data is now facing a decrease in sales. Meanwhile, based on preliminary research and problem exploration undertaken by the author reveal that Ganesha Sora continues to have low brand awareness. The purpose of this research is to increase Ganesha Sora brand awareness, identify major product attributes that influence customer purchase intentions, and to design suitable marketing strategies to increase the chances of sales. This study will include both quantitative and qualitative methods. For consumer analysis and hypothesis testing, the quantitative method is used. Data is gathered by distributing questionnaires to respondents who buy mozzarella cheese products in stores and online marketplaces. The output is then processed by SMART PLS. The qualitative method is utilized in preliminary research by interviewing 10 respondents and the business owner. According to the findings of this research, businesses can boost brand awareness by engaging in marketing activities such as sales promotion and advertising, which also have a beneficial impact on purchase intention. The following finding is about important product attributes that influence customer purchase intention, which include convenience, taste, and availability. From those findings, the author makes several recommendations based on internal and external analysis, along with a SWOT and TOWS analysis for Ganesha Sora to increase sales by entering and selling products to tourist attractions, offering testers or price discounts, and providing buy one get one e-vouchers on monthly occasions such as 11.11, 12.12, and so on. Ganesha Sora can conduct advertising activities such as creating an advertising video that highlights the product qualities and campaigns #BanggaDairyBuatanIndonesia to raise awareness. Ganesha Sora can launch a new product in a lighter weight variation and rent cold storage space in numerous potential places to deliver the attributes that consumers value.

KEYWORDS: Advertising, Brand Awareness, Product Attributes, Purchase Intention, Sales Promotion.

INTRODUCTION

The huge number of MSMEs in Indonesia cannot be isolated from the numerous obstacles and conditions of the Covid-19 pandemic, which have shifted consumption patterns of goods and services from offline to online, with a surge in internet traffic of 15-20%. This is a push to expedite digital transformation, such as conducting business through an online marketplace. Indonesia's digital economic potential is still huge, due to the country's fourth-largest population and internet penetration of 196.7 million people [1]. This forces business to be able to carry out digital transformation in their business so that they can keep up with the times, including Ganesha Sora. Currently, besides selling offline, Ganesha Sora must also carry out digital marketing in its business activities for the B2C segment. It is vital to improve the development of digital technology for producers. Nowadays, ms marketing that had previously been done conventionally was transformed into online marketing innovation [2]. Ganesha Sora run the company's B2B and B2C segments. B2C is the most impacted segment since they are still not focusing on their business through online marketplaces and are not raising efforts in offline promotion such as supermarkets and ranch markets. Because of the pandemic, they must adapt to the shift in consumer behavior from offline to online consumption patterns. This has an influence on Ganesha Sora's B2C sales, which are conducted through an offline store and several marketplaces such as Shopee, Tokopedia, and BliBli. According to the author's interview with the Director of Marketing and Sales, Ganesha Sora has to enhance brand awareness and improve their marketing approach in order to increase sales in the B2C segment especially in the online marketplaces.

BUSINESS ISSUES

According to the author's interview with the Director of Marketing and Sales, Ganesha Sora has to enhance brand awareness. CV. Ganesha Sora launched a business with a positive trend in 2015, however the COVID-19 Pandemic began to reach Indonesia in early 2020, specifically in March. CV. Ganesha Sora has a strong performance from the beginning until the middle of the year, but has suffered a big fall in the last few months of 2020. However, there was a fall in sales volume in the following months of 2022, notably in October, when total sales were only 1939 units. This caused in a dramatic fall in sales in the following years. Ganesha Sora also sells their product through marketplace, even if Tokopedia has many sold products, the number is still lower than their reseller. There are no sold products from Shopee and BliBli, indicating a problem in the B2C sector. Based on these symptoms, the author spoke with the head of marketing and sales, Mrs. Intan Dwinata, and discovered that she felt their potential customers were still unaware of Ganesha Sora's brand. Furthermore, they do not receive feedback from end users, therefore they do not know what the market desires. Based on the preliminary research through interview to 10 people, it is found that that 8 out of 10 people did not know or were unaware of this brand after being asked three times. The author asked those ten respondents about some product attributes so that Ganesha Sora would know what potential consumers wanted, which may increase their purchase intention, and it was discovered that the most important attributes from potential consumers are price, quality, brand familiarity, several promotional programs, and packaging. Other factors such as taste, certification, smell, presentation, and labeling may also impact potential consumers' purchasing intentions. It has been discovered that there are numerous marketing strategies that may influence purchase intention, which are mostly classified in marketing promotional mix such as sales promotion, advertising, and word of mouth. As the issue is decreased Mozzarella cheese sales, the author discovered various causes that produce root cause utilizing 5-why approaches, including a lack of awareness and still do not know the attributes to stay competitive. To enhance product sales, the corporation must raise brand awareness while also understanding the correct product attributes that would appeal to potential customers. Further research will be required to establish the strategies to raise Ganesha Sora's awareness in order to increase potential consumers' purchase intentions, which will affect Ganesha Sora's sales.

METHODOLOGY

The chosen research method is applied research. Applied research aims to apply research findings to tackle a specific problem that a firm or organization is facing [3]. The data will be tested and analyzed quantitatively using the SMART PLS program. SmartPLS is a well-known structural equation modelling software tool that uses partial least squares (PLS-SEM). PLS is useful for structural equation modelling, especially when the data distribution is skewed and there are few participants [4]. The primary data will be collected by several technique, which are: Observation, Interview, and Questionnaire. The questionnaire will be distributed to 200 respondents as the study's sample. A sampling unit is a research object that has several characteristics that reflect elements and will be utilized as samples in research. Non-probability sampling was employed in this study, which means that not everyone had the opportunity to be a sample, but respondents were chosen by the authors based on their own judgments as well as how easy it was for them to gather samples [5]. The questionnaire will employ a five-level likert scale with an interval scale. Because this questionnaire will be distributed online, it will be referred to as an online survey. The data from observation, interview, and questionnaire will be used to make internal and external analysis. The results of the internal analysis will be used to identify the company's strengths and weaknesses. Then external analysis will identify the company's opportunities and threats. The analysis will be finalized by TOWS analysis where TOWS Matrix is essentially a technique that allows analysts or researchers to create strategies for a certain company or organization in order to maximize strengths, to take advantage of opportunities, eliminate weaknesses, and avoid threats.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Customer Analysis

1) R- Square

The R square number describes how much a research model represents a phenomenon; here are the results:

Table 1. R-Square (Author, 2022)

Dependent Variable	R Square
Brand Awareness	0.585
Purchase Intention	0.445

- **R square = 0.585.** The first model (X1 Sales Promotion, X2 Word of Mouth, X3 Advertising, and Y Brand Awareness) can only explain 58.5% of the phenomenon. The remaining 41.5% is unrepresentable (there are outside variables that affect Brand Awareness).
- **R square = 0.445.** The first model (X1 Brand Awareness, X2 Product Attributes, and Y Purchase Intention) can only explain 44.5% of the phenomenon. The remaining 55.5% is unrepresentable (there are outside variables that affect Purchase Intention).

2) T-Statistics

If the t-statistic value is greater than the t-table value, the proposed study hypothesis is accepted, and vice versa. If any tvalues greater than 1.96 are significant [6]. Here are the outcomes:

Table 2. T-Statistics (SmartPLS, 2022)

Variable	Indicator	T-Statistics
Advertising	A1	36.076
	A2	32.599
	A3	26.463
	A4	33.152
Brand Awareness	BA1	57.079
	BA2	50.492
	BA3	82.608
Product Attributes	PA1	40.929
	PA2	32.701
	PA3	20.982
	PA4	15.823
	PA5	26.647
Variable	Indicator	T-Statistics
Purchase Intention	PI1	53.193
	PI2	37.384
	PI3	41.679
	PI4	32.649
Sales Promotion	SP1	16.058
	SP2	47.211
	SP3	32.654
	SP4	34.364
Word of Mouth	WM1	45.747
	WM2	51.137
	WM3	91.537

- Based on the table above, it is clear that all statistical T values are more than 1.96, implying that the association between latent variables is significant (it has a positive influence). Based on the questionnaire, this displays the level of agreement of respondents that agree that variable x influences variable y.
- The t-statistic value can be used since one of the study objectives is to identify the major product attributes that influence the customer's purchasing intention. According to the findings, the most important product features that influence purchase intention are PA1 (Convenience), PA2 (Availability), and PA5 (Taste).

3) P- Value

The p-value can also be used to determine significance. The criterion is significant if the p-value is less than 0.05 [6].

Here are the outcomes:

Table 3. P-Value (SmartPLS, 2022)

Variable	P Value
Advertising → Brand Awareness	0.002
Brand Awareness → Purchase Intention	0.000
Product Attributes → Purchase Intention	0.000
Sales Promotion → Brand Awareness	0.000
Word of Mouth → Brand Awareness	0.490

Based on the table above, it can be determined that all variables have a significant relationship (positive influence) except for “word-of-mouth variables on brand awareness”, implying that H1, H3, H4, and H5 are accepted and H2 is rejected, as shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Customer Analysis Conclusion (Author, 2022)

Hypothesis	P Value	Conclusion
H1: Sales Promotion has a positive influence on Brand Awareness.	Accepted	Sales Promotion has a positive influence on Brand Awareness.
H2: Word of Mouth has a positive influence on Brand Awareness	Rejected	Word of Mouth does not have a positive influence on Brand Awareness.
H3: Advertising has a positive influence on Brand Awareness.	Accepted	Advertising has a positive influence on Brand Awareness.
H4: Brand Awareness has a positive influence on Purchase Intention.	Accepted	Brand Awareness has a positive influence on Purchase Intention.
H5: Product attributes has a positive influence on Purchase Intention.	Accepted	Product attributes has a positive influence on Purchase Intention.

B. SWOT

- Strength (Internal Analysis):
 - 1) They have 3 variants of products.
 - 2) Already spreaded in many areas of Indonesia.
 - 3) It has savoury, non-bitter and creamy taste.

- 4) Achieved the 2021 Indonesian Food Innovation Awardee.
- 5) Pioneers of SMEs mozzarella producers, have halal and BPOM certification.
- 6) Have guidance from Prof. Lienda to produce good quality product.

• Weakness (Internal Analysis):

- 1) Social media promotion has not been maximized.
- 2) Discount are only available for large purchase.
- 3) The products are susceptible to temperature changes.
- 4) Lack of awareness.
- 5) Unactive YouTube Channel.

• Opportunity (External Analysis):

- 1) Ministerial regulation in Indonesia about the limitation amount of imported dairy product.
- 2) Improvement in the purchasing power of Indonesian after pandemic.
- 3) The advancement of technology in food production.
- 4) Positive influence of sales promotion and advertising towards brand awareness.
- 5) Positive influence of brand awareness and product attributes towards purchase intention.
- 6) Convenience, availability, and taste are significant product attributes which influence purchase intention.
- 7) There are not many players in the cheese business for MSMEs and there is a very large and growing market in the industry due to the consumer's culinary trends.

• Threat (External Analysis):

- 1) Lack of consistent level of promoting products on social media.
- 2) Unpredictable climate change related to the supplied material.
- 3) A strict law in Law No. 7 of 1996 which concern in food safety, quality, nutritions, diverse, and availability.
- 4) Prices of Ganesha Sora relatively expensive compared to other SMEs.

C. TOWS

• **S-O Strategy**

- 1) Entering and selling products to tourist attractions owned by the government or privately owned/local residents in Lembang while venturing into supermarkets and other ranch markets also continue to cooperate with reseller (S2, O1, O6).
- 2) Provide special prices for bundle purchases, both in supermarkets and marketplaces (S1, O2, O4).
- 3) Create an advertising in the form of a video that highlights the product attributes (S3, S4, S5, S6, O5, O7).
- 4) Launching a new product in a lighter weight variant (S1, S6, O3, O6, O7).

• **W-O Strategy**

- 1) Applying for financial assistance from the government through government websites such as OSS which will then be used for promotional activities (W1, W4, O1, O4, O7).
- 2) Carry out sales promotion activities in the form of testers or price discounts so consumers can recognize Ganesha Sora (W2, W4, O5, O6).
- 3) Give buy 1 get 1 e-vouchers to customers who review Mozzarella Ganesha Sora to be used for further purchases (W1, W2, O4).
- 4) Empowering employees to create Instagram/TikTok/Youtube content in the form of a short video/live video about the day's production story (W1, W5, O3, O4).

• **S-T Strategy**

- 1) Educating consumers either in person (in supermarkets) or via video (in e-commerce) about the characteristics of Mozzarella Ganesha Sora which match with current consumption pattern trends (S3, S4, S5, S6, T1, T3).

- 2) Creating mozzarella products at economical prices. For example, with lighter weight or in the form of other innovative products such as corndogs, brulle bombs, etc. (S1, S3, S6, T4).
- 3) Looking for and selecting additional milk suppliers from surrounding areas that are not bound (to become reserves). So, the quality of the cheese remains the same because the milk is still produced from Lembang. In the long term, Ganesha Ora is expected to have their own cattle farm so that the product's prices can decrease (S3, S6, T2, T4).

• W-T Strategy

- 1) Renting or cooperate with cold storage business in an area that already has a lot of customers or located far away (W3, T1, T2, T3).
- 2) Offering special price if the consumers buy product from the official store of Ganesha Sora's Tokopedia, Lazada, and Blibli (W2, T1, T4).
- 3) Create campaigns in various marketing media by highlighting #BanggaDairyBuatanIndonesia so that consumers are aware that there is mozzarella brand made in Indonesia which have competitive price and quality with imported products (W1, W4, W5, T3, T4).

CONCLUSION

Ganesha Sora is an MSMEs in the dairy food production industry in Indonesia. Ganesha Sora has been producing mozzarella cheese since 2015 and has gained halal certification, BPOM, and was named a Food Innovators Awardee in 2021, however the company still has low brand awareness and is experiencing sales declines. As the problem is a lack of awareness of Ganesha Sora, and based on the analysis, businesses can take out marketing activities such as sales promotion and advertising to build brand awareness because these two variables have a positive influence on brand awareness and purchase intention.

There are fourteen strategies which resulted from TOWS Analysis to be implemented by Ganesha Sora to increase their awareness and sales. The researcher now needs to adjust with the business' resources and capabilities, so that not all strategies can be implemented in a short time. **To increase sales**, the sales promotion activities can be carried out by making testers or price discounts, giving buy 1 get 1 free e-vouchers to some lucky consumers on monthly occasions such as 11.11, 12.12, and so on. **To raise awareness**, Ganesha Sora can carry out advertising activities such as creating an advertising video to raise awareness and educate consumers about the product qualities and campaigns #BanggaDairyBuatanIndonesia. The commercial video can also be placed on billboards in the area near Jl. Raya Lembang, which is popular with tourists on weekends.

The following finding is about important product attributes that influence customer purchase intention, which include convenience, taste, and availability. **Convenience** can be attained by launch a new product in a lighter weight variation, as well as by displaying the serving method on the packaging or through video advertisements. This strategy is also predicted make product prices more competitive to other MSMEs (although when compared to imported products they are already relatively cheap). **Taste and Availability** can be executed through supermarket testers, attractive product specifications advertisements, and renting or collaborating with cold storage businesses in various areas throughout Indonesia. As a result, the product will be available in many areas and the taste will be maintained because the mozzarella cheese does not suffer temperature changes for a long period of time.

RECCOMENDATION

Ganesha Sora's marketing activities, including sales promotion and advertising, should be improved in order to raise potential consumer awareness in the B2C segment. The company can also try to implement the new proposed marketing approach which are:

- 1) Launching a new product in a lighter weight variant.
- 2) Entering and selling products to tourist attractions owned by the government or privately owned/local residents in Lembang, venturing into supermarkets and other ranch markets, continue to cooperate with reseller.
- 3) Create an advertising to increase awareness and educate consumers in the form of a video that highlights the product attributes and campaigns #BanggaDairyBuatanIndonesia
- 4) Carry out sales promotion activities in the form of testers or price discounts so consumers can recognize Ganesha Sora.

- 5) Give buy 1 get 1 e-vouchers for some lucky consumers on monthly moments like 11.11, 12.12, etc. to be used for further purchases.
- 6) Renting or cooperate with cold storage business in an area that already has a lot of customers or located far away.

From those 6 strategies, it is hoped that perhaps not only awareness but also sales of Ganesha Sora would increase. Ganesha Sora must retain and improve its current product attributes, which are quite good (convenience, taste, and availability), in order to build consumer purchase intentions.

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